

Towards improved vibro-tactile P300 BCIs

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Abstract. The vibro-tactile P300 based Brain-Computer Interface is an interesting tool for severe impaired patients which cannot communicate using the muscular and visual vias. In this study we presented an improved tactile BCI for binary communication that reduces the wrong answers by adding a threshold to the decision value to achieve a valid answer, otherwise, the BCI gives an indecisive answer to the question. The threshold is calculated using a statistical test on the EEG, data recorded during the question to the patient. In total 7 tactile stimulators were placed on different parts of the subject's body. We tried the new BCI with 4 healthy subjects and using the statistical test they were able to get no wrong answers after 10 questions asked to each participant. The spelling accuracy and information transfer rate with and without statistical test are presented as well as examples of event related potentials.

Keywords: DOC, P300 speller, BCI.

1 Introduction

Brain-Computer Interfaces are devices which allow a person to control in some way a computer or a device connected to that computer. By definition there is no means of movement or other muscular activity necessary for that control [1]. Comparing such an interface to classic human-computer interfaces, like a computer mouse, keyboard, touchscreen or voice control, it is pretty clear that the BCI provides an inferior information transfer rate (ITR) and control accuracy. Bearing that in mind, but adding the fact that no motor control is necessary it seems clear that today's most BCI applications are thought for patients whose motor abilities are affected in one way or another. One of the first BCIs for communication was created by Niels Birbaumer and colleagues in 1999 [2]. They used slow cortical potentials (SCPs) for two patients suffering amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). To measure SCPs one needs only one EEG electrode, the drawback is that the voluntary control of those shifts in cortical potentials are very time consuming to be learned. In the publication of Birbaumer et al. two patients received more than 300 training sessions before they started free spelling, where one training day consisted of 6-12 sessions. For that reason, other control strategies were

used in the following years for BCI communication, most time based on event related potentials (ERP). These are electrical potentials, generated by the brain, that are related to specific internal or external events (e.g., stimuli, responses, decisions) [3]. Such events can be auditory-, tactile-, visual-, olfactory stimuli and even heat or pain. One can provide stimuli in a fast repetitive way with distinct frequencies or patterns and look for those patterns in the EEG. Such approaches are called SSVEP (see [1]), or code based visual evoked potentials (c-VEP, [4]). For SSVEPs Guger et al. demonstrated that 53 subjects reached a grand average accuracy of 95.5% after only a few minutes of training [5]. Volosyak et al. calculated a mean information transfer rate (ITR) of 40.23 bit/min and an accuracy of 97.83% with their c-VEP speller [6].

Another approach to utilize the ERP is done with P300 paradigms. There, the BCI is detecting a part of the ERP, the so called P300, which appears only after the user is focusing on a certain target stimulus. Hence, the trick is to present a series of distinguishable stimuli while the user waits for his pre-selected target stimulus to appear. As soon as this happens, the P300 will be generated, which can be detected and as a result the system knows which one was the target stimulus the user just chose. It is important to mention that one needs also nontarget stimuli, sometimes also called distractor stimuli for this approach to work. For a visual based P300 BCI one can use a big number of different characters, for example all the keys of computer keyboard and still gain high classification accuracy. For example Guger et al. found a mean accuracy of 91% with a 36 character speller and 81 participants [7].

BCIs using visual stimuli require the user to be able watching a computer screen or an array of LEDs and to shift his or her gaze from one point to another. Heavily impaired people may not be able to control a BCI in such a way. For those persons one could use other kinds of stimuli, for example auditory or tactile.

With a tactile P300 BCI, Eidel and Kübler recently reached 95% accuracy and 9.5 bits/min ITR after 5 sessions of training on 16 healthy participants [8]. In their first session they reached an ITR of 3.1 bits/minute and 65% accuracy. These results emphasize the influence of training even on P300 based BCIs. The same publication of Eidel and Kübler also presents an overview of recent tactile P300 publications with ITRs ranging mostly between 0.5 and 8 bits/minute and one publication showing an ITR of 20.73 bits/minute [9]. Auditory P300 provide a similar range of ITRs and accuracy, for example Halder et al. reached 2.46 bits/minute and accuracies of 78.6% [10]. It seems clear that the tactile and auditory paradigms cannot reach the same ITR as visual P300 BCI, because one cannot use as many classes as with a visual spelling matrix.

In 2014 we presented a tactile P300 BCI, using either two or three vibrotactile stimulators, placed on the users' body [11]. With the spelling paradigms, 6 locked-in patients reached an average accuracy of 55.3%. Possible results with the speller were YES, NO or an indecisive result in case the distractor stimuli received the highest classification result. For that work, we identified several problems that could have had negative influence on the performance. Firstly, we wanted to provide the user the possibility of an indecisive answer which is neither YES or NO. Such results would not only show if the user may not want to answer YES or NO, but it could also indicate that the user is currently just not attending the task. To implement this indecisive answer, we

allowed the distractors to be classified as well. The distractor stimuli were provided with higher probability than the two YES or NO stimuli, therefore the chance level of correctly choosing an answer was only 12.5%, which puts the reached 55.3% accuracy in a better light. But still, such an accuracy level must be considered questionable to be useful for a real communication task with patients. The second identified problem was that the distractor stimuli were provided all by the same vibrotactile stimulator. This could result in participants just ignoring the distractors, or rather not recognizing them in the sequence of stimuli, which could lead to a lower P300 amplitude after target stimuli.

For the current publication, we therefore thought on how to enhance the paradigm. We changed the classification in a sense that a distractor could not be longer a valid classification result. But, for still allowing patients to provide indecisive answers, we further introduced a statistical test, hence only a YES or NO answer, reaching a statistical threshold is considered a valid answer. Furthermore, we increased the number of vibrotactile stimulators from 3 to 7, distributed over the whole participant's body. The new paradigm was tested on 4 healthy participants. The accuracy as well as the ITR was calculated twice: with and without the statistical test. Examples of ERP plots are shown to demonstrate that subjects were able to generate distinct ERP patterns for each class (YES and NO), which can be detected by a classification algorithm.

2 Methods

2.1 Subjects

Four persons (all male, age 31.5 ± 6.5 years, see also Table 1) participated to the study. All participants signed an informed consent, the study was conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the responsible ethics committee (Ethikkommission des Landes Oberösterreich).

2.2 Material and Methods

The BCI was implemented using a computer running a Simulink model in g.HIsys (g.tec medical engineering, Austria). A biomedical amplifier (g.USBamp, g.tec medical engineering, Austria) was connected to the computer in order to acquire EEG data from the subject. The EEG cap used by the subject had 16 active electrodes. Fig. 1 A shows the positions according to the extended international 10/20 system. Red positions show the active electrodes, the yellow electrode marks the position of the ground, the reference electrode was placed to the right earlobe (blue) of the subject.

Seven vibro-tactile stimulator units (g.VIBROstim, g.tec medical engineering, Austria) were placed on different parts of the subject's body, see Fig. 1 B. The grey positions mark the places for the distractor stimulations: one on each ankle and shoulder, and another one near the navel. The green spot in the same figure marks the factor positions that was used to provide the answer YES (users' left hand). The red spot marks the position to provide the answer NO (right hand).

Fig. 1. A: Positions of the acquired EEG. Red spots are active electrodes, blue is the reference and yellow shows the position of the ground. B: Positions of the vibro-tactile stimulators. The green and red dots mark the two possible target positions and the grey dots the distractor positions.

2.3 Stimulation sequence

The sequence of stimuli for generating the ERPs was a sequence of vibrations of the vibro-tactile stimulators, doing so in a pseudorandomized order. Before the start of each session, it was explained that the participant should focus on the sequence of stimuli. If one wanted to express the answer YES, one should count each stimulus that was felt on the left hand. For selecting the answer NO, one was supposed to count the stimuli that were felt on the right hand. The counting of target stimuli helped the participants to remain focused on the task and created the P300 components that were used for classification.

One vibration stimulus with any stimulator lasted 100ms, the inter-stimulus interval was 75ms. For a precise recording of the timing, the stimulation device sent in parallel a trigger impulse to the digital input of the amplifier each time it switched on a stimulator.

One question was composed of 25 cycles, and each cycle had 8 trials. One trial represents a single stimulus of one of the vibro-tactile stimulators. In every cycle there was at least one trial belonging to one of the seven stimulators, and only one belonging to each of the left and right stimulators.

2.4 One session

Each participant did one training run, followed by 10 online communication runs. The training run was a sequence of 6 questions where the participant shall select 3 times the answer YES and 3 times NO. In each communication run, the participant was asked one questions with known answer, for example “Do you currently live in Vienna”.

The training run lasted 5 minutes, including short pauses between the questions. One run (question) of the online communication test lasted 37 seconds.

2.5 Feature expression and classification

EEG data were acquired with a sample rate of 256 Hz. Applied filters were a highpass with cutoff frequency at 0.5Hz, a lowpass at 30Hz and additionally a notch filter at 50Hz to suppress power line interference.

After that, the data was triggered into single trials. One trial contained 100ms before the stimulus onset and 600ms after that. The segment before each stimulus was used for an individual baseline correction of each trial and channel, by subtracting the mean value of that baseline from the whole trial data.

Consecutively, data got down-sampled by factor 24, using a lowpass filter before to not violate the Nyquist criterium. With the remaining samples, we generated the feature space (6 samples per channel). Classification was done using the time-variant linear discriminant analysis according to Grünwald et al. [12]. This method uses a time-variant feature space, accounting different phases of the ERP. Since 25 trials of each target were used for classification, the single LDA distances got summed up to generate one final decision of each character.

2.6 Indecisive answers

To decide if an answer was indecisive, a threshold was calculated. If the LDA was below the threshold, the answer was considered indecisive. For that, a gaussian distribution of LDA distances was created by splitting up the test-data and using a bootstrapping approach. Having the gaussian distribution of LDA distances one can decide if the LDA distance calculated with the whole set of test-data is withing the percentile 45 and 55, then the answer is indecisive, otherwise not.

2.7 ERP plots

For the ERP plots the single trials, as described above, got averaged after baseline correction. The plot show target trials in blue and distractor trials in red-dashed line. Additionally, Mann-Whitney significance tests has been done to indicate areas with significant difference between the lines. Those areas are marked in green in the ERP plots.

2.8 ITR

To calculate the ITR, one needs to calculate the average transferred information per answer and the time needed to select one answer. The transferred information depends on the number of correctly provided answers, in worst case, if this is only about 50% then the answer is not better than random, hence no information would be transferred. The number of bits (B) is calculated with the following formula:

$$B = \log_2 N + P \log_2 P + (1 - P) \log_2 \frac{1 - P}{N - 1}$$

Where N is the number of possible answers, and P the reached accuracy. Since the subject were always asked to either answer yes or no, N was set to 2. The accuracy P was calculated for each participant with the number of correct answered questions divided by the number of asked questions. Having calculated B, one can calculate the ITR with:

$$ITR = B/T_{average}$$

$T_{average}$ is the average time needed to provide one answer which is either yes or no. Hence, that value was constant when only binary classification is allowed (37 seconds). If indecisive classification is allowed too, the average time is calculated with:

$$T_{average} = \frac{\text{asked questions}}{\text{yes and no answered questions}} 37s$$

3 Results

Table 1. Results of the four subjects calculated two times with the same data. Left: Accuracy and ITR if no indecisive answers were allowed, Right: indecisive answers were allowed.

ID	Age (y)	No indecisive answers		Indecisive answers	
		Acc. (%)	ITR (B/min)	Acc. (%)	ITR (B/min)
S1	40	100	1.6	100	1.5
S2	33	90	1.4	100	1.5
S3	26	100	1.6	100	1.5
S4	27	90	1.4	100	1.3
MEAN	31.5	95	1.5	100	1.4
STD	6.5	5.8	0.1	0	0.1

Table 1 shows the four subjects with their age, accuracy in percent and ITR in bits/minute. The accuracy and ITR was calculated two times on the same data. The first time (left part of the table) each question resulted in an answer YES or NO, so the test for

indecisive answers was not applied. In the second case (right part of the table) that test was applied and answers got classified indecisive if they did not reach the threshold. S2 and S3 could increase their accuracy from 90% to 100% because their one wrong answer was classified indecisive in the second case.

Indecisive answers are not considered wrong for the accuracy calculation. The change of wrong answers to indecisive answers is further visualized in Fig. 2. The bars marked with A show the results without indecisive answers. Bars marked with B show the results with calculation of possible indecisive answers. The number of correct answers is indicated with green color, the number of wrong answers is indicated with red color and the indecisive answers are plotted in grey color. The ITR of both calculations can be seen in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Number of correctly provided answers of the four participants. The two last columns show the mean values of all subjects. Bars marked with A: no indecisive answers allowed, B indecisive answers allowed.

Fig. 3. ERP of S3 at location Cz. Blue line: averaged trials when target stimuli were delivered with the tactor on the left hand. Red- dashed line: averaged distractor trials. Green areas: significant differences between the two lines.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the ERP plots of participant S3 on position Cz. To generate the plots EEG data of the training run was used, where each participant shall focus for three questions on the left hand stimuli and for three questions on the right hand stimuli. In Fig. 3 one sees the averaged trials of left hand stimuli (blue line) and the averaged distractor data from the same two questions (red dashed line). These stimuli were used to provide the answer yes. The green marked areas show the significant differences between the two lines. The vertical dashed line at 0s shows the onset time of the stimuli. There is a big positive peak at 100ms and a broad positive peak around 300ms after the stimulus onset. Fig. 4 shows the other two questions. The shape of averaged target trials is quite different to the ones in Fig. 3.

Fig. 4. ERP of S3 at location Cz. Blue line: averaged trials when target stimuli were delivered with the tactor on the right hand. Red, dashed line: averaged distractor trials. Green areas: significant differences between the two lines.

4 Discussion

With this publication, we would like to demonstrate two things: First, the classification accuracy of our new paradigm and secondly the influence of a new approach that shall only present an answer if the results have a strong enough tendency towards one result or the other, and otherwise mark the result as indecisive. In future, the BCI shall be used by heavily impaired patients, who cannot use visual P300 speller or other means of communication. Therefore, we rather focus on the spelling accuracy than speed, which seems more important in our point of view for these applications. Also, the indecisive answers are thought to be useful for users who may not be able to indicate to the outer world if they currently do not want to use the tool at all, or just don't want to say yes or no to a specific question.

The accuracy could be increased from 95% to 100% with the statistical test for indecisive answers, but the ITR decreased from 1.5 to 1.4 bits/minute. This is consistent with our defined goals, to have the best possible accuracy, even if the speed suffers. In a real scenario an indecisive answer could mean that one has to ask the same question again to wait if a significant classification result could be reached.

The ITR of 1.4 bits/minute is worse compared to most of other studies as presented in Eidel and Kübler [8]: between 0.5 and 20.73 bits/minute. But those results were often achieved after several sessions of training and none reached the 100% accuracy our approach showed.

Maybe the biggest caveat for our study is that the future target user group, people with impairments have not been covered by the participants of this study. But we wanted to first validate if the system works at all, and shows a good performance, before going to patients. It is clear though that the achieved results of ITR and accuracy will not be perfectly transferable to patients.

The example plot of ERP in Fig. 3 shows a late P100 and a broad P300 peak for target stimuli. This broad peak goes in accordance to our previous work where the same tactile stimulators were used for generating ERP, see for example [13]. The ERP in Fig. 4 are of the same subject, but with the target stimuli presented on the right hand instead of the left hand. The ERP looks quite unusual, especially for a healthy control. We chose these plots on purpose because they demonstrate something worth discussing. For reaching a good spelling accuracy one does not need to generate textbook like ERPs, or at least not for both classes. If the subject's ERPs for right hand target stimulation would be the same as for distractor stimulation, while the ERPs for left hand stimulation are as shown in Fig. 3, the classifier would be still perfectly able to distinguish the two classes. We did not test if users can, on purpose, elicit an indecisive answer by trying to ignore the stimulation sequence. We could speculate that such a user as S3 could have troubles in doing so. Something that could be investigated deeper in future studies.

Our next step is to validate the approach on a bigger number of healthy users, and eventually adapt it, based on the lessons learned with that data. After that having done successful, we would like to recruit patients for tests.

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References

1. Wolpaw JR, Birbaumer N, McFarland DJ, et al (2002) Brain–computer interfaces for communication and control. *Clinical Neurophysiology* 113:767–791. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1388-2457\(02\)00057-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1388-2457(02)00057-3)
2. Birbaumer N, Ghanayim N, Hinterberger T, et al (1999) A spelling device for the paralysed. *Nature* 398:297–298
3. Luck SJ (2014) An introduction to the event-related potential technique. MIT press
4. Bin G, Gao X, Wang Y, et al (2009) VEP-based brain-computer interfaces: time, frequency, and code modulations [Research Frontier. *IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine* 4:22–26. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCI.2009.934562>
5. Guger C, Allison BZ, Großwindhager B, et al (2012) How Many People Could Use an SSVEP BCI? *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 6:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2012.00169>
6. Volosyak I, Rezeika A, Benda M, et al (2020) Towards solving of the Illiteracy phenomenon for VEP-based brain-computer interfaces. *Biomed Phys Eng Express* 6:035034. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2057-1976/ab87e6>
7. Guger C, Daban S, Sellers E, et al (2009) How many people are able to control a P300-based brain–computer interface (BCI)? *Neuroscience Letters* 462:94–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2009.06.045>
8. Eidel M, Kübler A (2020) Wheelchair Control in a Virtual Environment by Healthy Participants Using a P300-BCI Based on Tactile Stimulation: Training Effects and Usability. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience* 14:. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnhum.2020.00265>
9. Herweg A, Gutzeit J, Kleih S, Kübler A (2016) Wheelchair control by elderly participants in a virtual environment with a brain-computer interface (BCI) and tactile stimulation. *Biological psychology* 121:117–124
10. Halder S, Rea M, Andreoni R, et al (2010) An auditory oddball brain–computer interface for binary choices. *Clinical Neurophysiology* 121:516–523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2009.11.087>
11. Lugo ZR, Rodriguez J, Lechner A, et al (2014) A vibrotactile p300-based brain–computer interface for consciousness detection and communication. *Clinical EEG and neuroscience* 45:14–21
12. Gruenwald J, Znobishchev A, Kapeller C, et al (2019) Time-Variant Linear Discriminant Analysis: A new gold-standard classifier for invasive brain-computer interfaces? Napa, CA, USA
13. Ortner R, Spataro R, Scharinger J, et al (2017) Vibro-tactile Evoked Potentials for BCI Communication of people with Disorders of Consciousness and locked-in syndrome. In: *Proceedings of the Graz Brain-Computer Interface Conference 2017*